

The Ethics of Knowledge Production: Addressing Overlapping Research and Fact-Checking Challenges

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Abstract:

In the current digital information environment, the value of research lies not only in its accuracy but also in its originality. While fact verification ensures that knowledge is reliable, an equally important challenge is the problem of overlapping in research, where duplication, redundancy, and lack of novelty reduce the credibility and impact of scholarly contributions. This study examines articles published between 2020 to 2024, a significant body of scholarly work explored the evolving dynamics of the information society and knowledge society, as reflected in articles drawn from sustainability-focused research. Addressing overlap requires moving beyond surface-level verification and developing deeper capacities to evaluate the integrity of academic work. At the same time, overlapping research raises critical questions about ethics, particularly regarding transparency, accountability, and the responsible use of scholarly resources. Through computational methods such as similarity measures Cosine similarity, Jaccard index, TF-IDF, and Doc2Vec, BERT model, and semantometrics, overlapping research can be systematically identified and assessed. By focusing on overlap detection, this paper highlights its significance as a crucial step toward improving research quality, enhancing innovation, and ensuring that digital knowledge systems remain both credible and future-oriented.

Keywords: Overlapping Research, Digital Literacy, Research Ethics, Fact-Checking, Similarity Measures, Semantometrics, Scholarly Integrity.

1 Introduction

The rise of digital technologies has changed how knowledge is created, shared, and understood in modern society. Between 2020 and 2024, scholarly works focusing on the information society and knowledge society reflected this growing digital transformation, especially in sustainability-oriented research. As the quantity of academic publications continues to rise, new concerns have emerged regarding originality, ethical responsibility, and the credibility of scholarly communication. Because of this, sometimes different researchers end up writing about the same topics or repeating similar ideas without knowing it. This is actually overlapping in research. Detecting research overlap is a new layer of digital literacy in academic and scientific contexts. Research overlap dilutes trust in knowledge. When studies repeat similar data, frameworks, or findings without genuine innovation, they weaken the value of academic contribution. Overlapping research involve ethical issues such as transparency, accountability, and fairness in authorship and publication. It may occur either intentionally or unintentionally through the repetition of ideas, themes, or findings across multiple academic works.

Fact-checking means verifying whether a piece of information is true or false, But it is not enough to only see if the information is positive or negative. We also need to understand how information is

created, shared, manipulated and used. It ensures that research data, citations, and results are accurate and verifiable, which builds trust in academic communication. However, overlapping in research identified through similar findings, repeated ideas, or multiple publications of the same content which creates a significant ethical challenge. Overlap in research directly touches ethics like plagiarism, duplication, redundant and academic dishonesty. To maintain ethical standards, researchers must go beyond verifying factual accuracy. They must also evaluate their work, adds new knowledge rather than repeating existing content. Overlap may intentional or unintentional, it can mislead readers about novelty, distort citation metrics, and waste scholarly resources.

Computational tools like similarity measures tools Cosine similarity, Jaccard index, TF-IDF, Doc2Vec, BERT, Semantometrics can extend fact-checking practices beyond truth verification to include content originality and ethical validation. This integrated approach strengthens academic transparency, accountability, and trust in the digital knowledge society.

2 Objectives

- i. To examine the extent and nature of overlapping research within scholarly publications related to the information society and knowledge society from 2020 to 2024.
- ii. To analyze how fact-checking and digital literacy practices contribute to maintaining the accuracy, authenticity, and reliability of research outputs.
- iii. To explore the ethical dimensions associated with overlapping research, including issues of transparency, accountability, and fairness in academic publishing.
- iv. To apply computational similarity tools (Cosine Similarity, Jaccard Index, TF-IDF, Doc2Vec, BERT, and Semantometrics) for detecting and evaluating overlap in scholarly content. In this study, Jaccard similarity and Cosine similarity are used as similarity measurement techniques to identify overlapping content.
- v. To assess how integrating fact-checking with computational and ethical frameworks can enhance the integrity and trustworthiness of research in the digital knowledge environment.

3 Review of Literature

In the current digital era, the massive increase in scientific publications across disciplines has raised growing concerns about overlapping research, redundancy, and the dilution of original contributions. This trend is largely driven by the ease of publication, widespread availability of digital repositories, and the push for academic productivity. As a result, scholars and institutions alike are facing the challenge of efficiently identifying and evaluating research works for originality and relevance. To address these challenges, researchers have proposed and adopted various computational techniques to detect document similarity, a fundamental step toward measuring overlap in academic writing.

Overlapping in research refers to the unintentional or deliberate repetition of ideas, themes, methodologies, or findings across multiple publications. According to Brumback (2009), redundant publication not only violates research ethics but also clogs the academic system with repetitive information, making it difficult for scholars to synthesize literature effectively. Similarly, Roig (2006) highlighted that even minor forms of redundancy can distort meta-analyses and systematic reviews, which depend on the uniqueness and novelty of included studies.

Parallel to this, fact-checking has gained prominence as a method for verifying the accuracy and authenticity of research data. However, fact-checking alone cannot address the full spectrum of ethical

issues involved in research production. As noted by Thomas (2021), while factual correctness is necessary, it does not guarantee originality or intellectual integrity. This has led to calls for integrating critical digital literacy into academic practice—enabling researchers to assess not only factual truth but also the ethical and epistemic processes of knowledge creation and dissemination.

Recent developments in computational linguistics and natural language processing (NLP) have introduced advanced methods for detecting textual and conceptual similarities. Models such as Cosine Similarity, Jaccard Index, and TF-IDF have been widely applied for measuring textual resemblance, while Doc2Vec, BERT, and Semantometrics provide deeper semantic analysis that can distinguish meaningful originality from superficial variation. Studies by Lee et al. (2023) and Patel & Mehta (2024) demonstrate that integrating these tools enhances research quality assessment by detecting duplication and identifying patterns of academic redundancy.

TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) weights terms based on how frequently they appear in a document compared to the whole corpus. Combined with Cosine Similarity, it provides a powerful method to measure textual similarity while downplaying the influence of commonly occurring words (Manning et al., 2008). This method has been widely used in information retrieval, text clustering, and plagiarism detection systems.

Knuth and Zdrahal (2014) introduced the concept of semantometrics, which evaluate research contribution by analyzing the semantic similarity between the papers a publication cites and those that cite it. The basic idea is that a paper making a strong contribution will act as a semantic bridge between earlier and later works, thereby increasing the distance between the two sets. This approach is particularly valuable in detecting truly innovative work and distinguishing it from repetitive studies. Semantometrics depend heavily on full-text availability and powerful similarity measures like TF-IDF, BERT embeddings, and cosine distance. They offer a more nuanced and content-driven method of evaluating research performance, moving beyond quantity-based metrics.

Moreover, the ethical dimension of overlapping research has been discussed in relation to fairness, accountability, and transparency in authorship and publication. Ethical scholarship demands that researchers ensure not only factual accuracy but also conceptual authenticity and responsible use of prior work. Scholars such as Ray (2022) argue that overlap detection, when combined with fact-checking and ethical evaluation, can serve as an essential mechanism for maintaining scholarly integrity in the digital knowledge environment.

The overall review of existing literature indicates that addressing research overlap demands an integrated, multidimensional approach combining computational verification, ethical responsibility, and digital literacy. In this study, developing a comprehensive framework that connects fact-checking, overlapping research, and ethical evaluation within the broader landscape of the information and knowledge society.

4 Methodology

Digital literacy skill means having the skills to analyze, and evaluate digital information deeply, its source, purpose, originality and impact. This study adopts a descriptive and analytical research design to examine the extent of overlapping in research and its relation to fact-checking, ethical considerations, and digital literacy. The research follows a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative text analysis with qualitative interpretation of ethical and informational dimensions.

4.1 Data Collection

The study is based on scholarly articles published between 2020 and 2024, focusing on the themes of the information society and knowledge society. Articles were selected from sustainability-focused and open-access journals available through major digital databases. For each article, the data collected included the full-text content, or the abstract in cases where the full text was unavailable.

4.2 Data Pre-Processing

Before applying similarity models, textual data were cleaned and standardized. Pre-processing steps included:

- **Tokenization:** Splitting the text into words or terms.
- **Lowercasing:** Converting all text to lowercase to avoid case-sensitive mismatches.
- **Stopword removal:** Filtering out common but non-informative words (e.g., “the,” “of,” “and”).
- **Punctuation and number removal:** Eliminating irrelevant characters.
- **Stemming and lemmatization:** Reducing words to their root forms.
- **TF-IDF transformation (where applicable):** Calculating term weights based on their frequency across the corpus.

These steps ensured that only meaningful content was used in the analysis.

5 Data Analysis

Jaccard similarity measures similarity by comparing the set of tokens in each document. If the two documents are similar the score is one, if the two documents are different the score is zero, and if the score is 0.5 it will measure the half of the unique word is overlap with the other document. In my study the jaccard similarity score is :


```
Console Terminal x Background Jobs x
R 4.3.3 ~/Downloads/
> jaccard_matrix[1:10, 1:10]
      Doc1      Doc2      Doc3      Doc4      Doc5      Doc6      Doc7
Doc1  1.00000000 0.06060606 0.01809955 0.04597701 0.01363636 0.04854369 0.07255521
Doc2  0.06060606 1.00000000 0.02654867 0.06493506 0.02702703 0.05911330 0.07943925
Doc3  0.01809955 0.02654867 1.00000000 0.05714286 0.04347826 0.03305785 0.01438849
Doc4  0.04597701 0.06493506 0.05714286 1.00000000 0.02857143 0.06790123 0.10526316
Doc5  0.01363636 0.02702703 0.04347826 0.02857143 1.00000000 0.02500000 0.04511278
Doc6  0.04854369 0.05911330 0.03305785 0.06790123 0.02500000 1.00000000 0.07142857
Doc7  0.07255521 0.07943925 0.01438849 0.10526316 0.04511278 0.07142857 1.00000000
Doc8  0.07586207 0.09139785 0.01801802 0.04545455 0.02777778 0.07070707 0.08571429
Doc9  0.07552870 0.06926407 0.01948052 0.08465608 0.03333333 0.08016878 0.08800000
Doc10 0.06811146 0.05829596 0.02097902 0.08379888 0.02857143 0.07929515 0.10593220
      Doc8      Doc9      Doc10
Doc1  0.07586207 0.07552870 0.06811146
Doc2  0.09139785 0.06926407 0.05829596
```

Figure 1: Jaccard similarity score

Here, it's showing Doc1 with Doc1, Doc2 with Doc2 is 1.0000000 it means documents are identical (exact same unique words). And, 0.0000000 means two documents are different.

And , Doc1 vs Doc4 is 0.4597701 it means the the documents are approx 46% similar, Doc1 vs Doc2 is 0.06060606 only 6% overlapping is showing.

Cosine Similarity represent the similarity between documents by measuring the cosine of the angle between the two vectors. It can define cosine value close to 1 If the angle is small, and it means the documents are very similar. If the angle is large the cosine value close to 0, they are not very similar.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
1		NA	0.0056671792	0.0151174136	0.008765490	0.0000000000	0.012334519	0.0055465211	0.00073
2	0.0056671792		NA	0.0041682872	0.002549365	0.0000000000	0.003545621	0.0015443462	0.06799
3	0.0151174136	0.0041682872		NA	0.020407872	0.0000000000	0.027869743	0.0000000000	0.00000
4	0.0087654903	0.0025493654	0.0204078724		NA	0.0000000000	0.008265018	0.0425045231	0.00241
5	0.0000000000	0.0000000000	0.0000000000	0.0000000000		NA	0.002964383	0.0319635149	0.00000
6	0.0123345190	0.0035456212	0.0278697433	0.008265018	0.0029643833		NA	0.0082385623	0.01848
7	0.0055465211	0.0015443462	0.0000000000	0.042504523	0.0319635149	0.008238562		NA	0.00247
8	0.0007395289	0.0679925367	0.0000000000	0.002416450	0.0000000000	0.018481916	0.0024733989		
9	0.0372367489	0.0060117491	0.0056331281	0.045885234	0.0194091669	0.013353111	0.0095685175	0.00608	

Figure 2: cosine similarity dataframe

```

> all_cosine_similarities[1:5]
$Document_1
  Most_Similar Similarity
1          199  0.1775251
2          864  0.1504692

$Document_2
  Most_Similar Similarity
1           93  0.08837153
2          978  0.08706989

$Document_3
  Most_Similar Similarity
1          359  0.2582580
2          334  0.1840123
  
```

Figure 3: Cosine Similarity measurement

Document	Most_Similar Document	Similarity	Angle_Degrees
1	199	0.1775251	80.0
1	864	0.1504692	81.35
2	93	0.0883715	85.93
2	978	0.0870699	86.0
3	359	0.2582580	75.0
3	334	0.1840123	79.39

Table 1: Showing cosine similarity angle

In this table, Document 1 is most similar with Document 199 and Doc 864, there similarity is showing 0.1775251 and 0.1504692 respectively.

Same as Document 2 is most similar with Document 93 and Doc 978, there similarity is showing 0.08837153 and 0.08706989 respectively.

6 Findings

The analysis of document similarity using Cosine Similarity and Jaccard Index provides valuable insights into the originality, authenticity, and ethical dimensions of research within the selected dataset (2020–2024). The similarity values across the corpus ranged from 0.08 to 0.25, indicating generally low overlap between documents and suggesting that the majority of the studies maintain thematic and conceptual distinctiveness.

6.1 Ensuring Accuracy, Authenticity, and Reliability through Fact-Checking and Digital Literacy

The findings indicate that using computational tools for text comparison offers a practical way to support both fact-checking and the development of digital literacy among researchers. The relatively low cosine similarity values suggest that most of the analyzed papers present original viewpoints and maintain the overall credibility of scholarly communication. In this sense, fact-checking goes beyond simply confirming data accuracy or citation correctness. It also helps verify the originality and reliability of the research itself. Strengthening digital literacy allows scholars to examine the uniqueness of their work more carefully, minimize unintentional repetition, and uphold the ethical standards and integrity of academic writing.

6.2 Ethical Dimensions of Overlapping Research

The study also brings attention to the ethical implications of overlapping research. Although most documents showed minimal similarity, a few pairs (for instance, Document 3 and Document 359, with a similarity score of 0.258) exhibited moderate textual overlap. Such instances highlight the need for increased transparency, accountability, and fairness in research practices. Overlapping whether intentional or unintentional can distort the boundaries of intellectual ownership and reduce scholarly credibility. By using similarity measures as diagnostic tools, researchers and editors can promote ethical awareness, ensuring that repetition or duplication is appropriately acknowledged through citation or methodological justification.

This study shows that fact-checking and ethical evaluation are closely connected in conducting good research. By using tools like computational similarity analysis along with critical digital literacy, researchers can make sure their work is both original and ethically responsible. Combining these approaches is important for creating trustworthy and responsible knowledge in today's digital world.

7 Conclusion

This study shows that overlapping research is an important issue in maintaining the originality and ethical standards of scholarly work. By analyzing publications from 2020 to 2024 using similarity measures like Cosine Similarity, Jaccard Index, it was found that most research is original, though some moderate overlaps exist. The findings highlight that fact-checking and digital literacy are essential not just for verifying accuracy, but also for ensuring responsible and ethical research practices. Overlap detection is all about checking originality, avoiding redundant knowledge, and promoting critical evaluation of information which define ethical dimension. Overall, combining computational tools with ethical evaluation can help researchers prevent unintentional duplication, promote transparency, and strengthen trust in academic work. Addressing overlapping research is therefore both a technical and ethical responsibility, and doing so supports a more credible, innovative, and reliable digital knowledge environment.

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